

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**FORMULATION AND EVALUTION OF MESALMAINE
SUSTAINED RELEASE TABLETS BY USING NATURAL
POLYMER****¹P. Adi Narayana Reddy, ²Dr. J . N. Suresh Kumar, ³B Sanjeevarao, ⁴K. Nirmal Jyothi,
⁵*K . Naga Pushyami, ⁶Sk. Neelima, ⁷V. Sahithi Sai**¹M.Pharm Assistant Professor, Narasaraopeta Institute Of Pharmaceutical Sciences ,
Narasaraopeta.²M.Pharm,Ph.D, Fage, Principal, Narasaraopeta Institute Of Pharmaceutical Sciences ,
Narasaraopeta.³⁻⁷Narasaraopeta Institute Of Pharmaceutical Sciences , Narasaraopeta.E Mail : kotturinagapushyami@gmail.com**Abstract:**

Evaluation of sustained release tablets of Mesalamine using natural polymers to enhance therapeutic efficacy and patient compliance in the treatment of inflammatory bowel disease. Sustained release systems are designed to deliver the drug at a controlled rate over an extended period, thereby reducing dosing frequency. Tablets were prepared by wet granulation using natural polymers such as xanthan gum and guar gum in varying concentrations as release-retarding agents.

Pre-compression parameters including angle of repose, bulk density, tapped density, Carr's index, and Hausner's ratio indicated satisfactory flow properties of the powder blends. Post-compression evaluation showed that the tablets met acceptable limits for weight variation, thickness, hardness, friability, and drug content. In-vitro dissolution studies were conducted for 24 hours using 0.1 N HCl for the first 2 hours followed by pH 6.8 phosphate buffer to simulate gastrointestinal conditions. Formulations with higher polymer concentrations exhibited prolonged and controlled drug release. The optimized formulation demonstrated a desirable sustained release profile. The formulation (f6) created has a highest drug release rate of all formulations tested.

Key words: Mesalamine, Sustained release, Natural polymers, xanthan gum, ftir

Corresponding author:

K . Naga Pushyami,
Narasaraopeta Institute Of Pharmaceutical Sciences ,
Narasaraopeta.
E Mail : kotturinagapushyami@gmail.com

QR CODE

Please cite this article in press K . Naga Pushyami et al., Formulation And Evalution Of Mesalmaine Sustained Release Tablets By Using Natural Polymer., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2026; 13(03).

INTRODUCTION:

Any drug delivery system's principal objective is to deliver a therapeutic dose of medication to a target site such that the required drug concentration can be quickly attained and subsequently maintained. Drugs might be administered locally or systemically at the colon. Topical therapy is possible with local distribution, but drugs that are more effectively used in the colon have less systemic side effects. Multiple severe obstacles to drug distribution are present in the gastrointestinal tract. The possibility for the administration of proteins and peptides has made colonic drug delivery more significant than only the delivery of medications for the treatment of local colon disorders. Due to decreased diversity and intensity of enzyme activities as well as a pH that is close to neutral, the colon presents less unfriendly conditions for medication transport. The colon may also be the optimal location for medication administration due to its extended residence period and low digestive enzymatic activity, which may be beneficial for prolonged drug delivery. Colonic delivery is advantageous for the treatment of colonic disorders like ulcerative colitis, Crohn's disease, colon cancer, and amoebiasis. It also offers the potential to give macromolecular medications orally. The colon is regarded as an adequate place for the absorption of many medications due to the lack of digestive enzymes and the prolonged transit time.

Mesalamine is absorbed in the upper GI tract, yet it has direct anti-inflammatory effects on the irritated mucosa of the colon and rectum. It functions by preventing the body from generating a certain chemical that can induce inflammation. By reducing prostaglandin production in the colon and blocking cyclooxygenase, mesalamine reduces inflammation. To improve its effects, numerous kinds of release-controlled oral formulations of mesalamine have been created.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

MATERIALS:

S.No.	Materials	Company name
1.	Mesalamine	Divi's laboratories, Hyderabad.
2.	Xanthan gum	Nice chemicals Pvt.Ltd Kochi-24
3.	Micro crystalline cellulose	Indian research powders , madras-11, India
4.	Talc	Nice chemicals Pvt.Ltd Kochi-24
5.	Magnesium stearate	Oxford laboratories Mumbai, India
6.	Poly vinyl pyrrolidone – K30	Nice chemicals Pvt.Ltd Kochi-24
7.	Iso propyl alcohol	Nice chemicals Pvt.Ltd Kochi-24

Table 1: Materials used

METHODS:

Construction of calibration curve by UV- visible spectrophotometer

Calibration curve of Mesalamine in 0.1 N HCl

Preparation of standard stock solution:

Weigh and transfer about 100mg of Mesalamine and 100ml 0.1NHCl in a 100ml volumetric flask

Preparation of test solution from stock solution:

Take 10ml and dilute to 100 ml with 0.1NHCl stock solution λ max is calculated by using concentration in the range of 200-700 nm.

Standard graph Of Mesalamine

Weigh and transfer about 100 mg of Mesalamine into 100 ml volumetric flask, add 0.1NHCl solution, make up the volume to 100 ml with 0.1NHCl solution. From the stock solution, take 10ml and dilute to 100ml with 0.1NHCl, working solution is prepared. From the stock solution 2,4,6,8 and 10 μ g/ml were prepared and the absorbance was measured at 232 nm.

Calibration curve of Mesalamine using pH 6.0

Phosphate buffer 10mg of drug was dissolved in phosphate buffer pH 6.0 and final volume was making up to 100ml volumetric flask. The stock solution concentration was 100 μ g/ml obtained. It was diluted with phosphate buffer pH 6.0 to obtain solution in concentration range 2,4,6,8,10 μ g/ml. Absorbance of μ g/ml solution was measured between 200-400nm by using spectrophotometer.

Calibration curve of mesalamine using pH 6.8

Phosphate buffer

Accurately weighed 10 mg of drug, dissolved in sufficient volume of phosphate buffer pH 6.8 and then made volume up to 100 ml with phosphate buffer pH 6.8 and then working solutions of different concentrations 2,4,6,8,10(μ g/ml) were prepared. The absorbance was obtained at λ max 301nm and calibration curve was plotted between concentration and absorbance.

PREFORMULATION STUDIES

FTIR Studies

FTIR spectrophotometer is used to perform Drug excipient compatibility between drugs and excipients using Brukers Alpha Spectrophotometer. Under high compaction pressure and using the disc method, sample powder was thoroughly combined with potassium bromide at a 100:1 ratio in a glass mortar and pestle. The produced pellets were submitted to IR spectral analysis at wave number ranges of 4000 - 400 cm⁻¹.

PRECOMPRESSION EVALUATION

Bulk density

The mass of the powder divided by the bulk volume is known as the bulk density.

$$\text{Bulk density} = \text{Mass} / \text{bulk volume}$$

Tapped Density

It is the ratio of total mass of the powder to the tapped volume of the powder.

$$\text{Tapped Density} = \text{Mass of powder} / \text{Tapped}$$

volume

Angle of repose

Angle of repose defined as the maximum angle possible between surface of pile of powder and horizontal plane. It is characteristic related to inter particulate friction or resistance movement between particles.

$$\Theta = \tan^{-1}h/r$$

Hausner's Ratio

Hausner's ratio is correlated to the flowability of a powder or granular material. If it is greater than 1.25 is considered to be indication of poor flowability.

$$\text{Tapped density/ Bulk density}$$

% Compressibility

Percent compressibility of powder mix was determined by carr's compressibility index.

$$\text{Carr's index (\%)} = \frac{\text{TTBD}}{\text{BD}}$$

– LBD / TBD x 100 Where , BD: Bulk density , TD: Tapped density

Preparation of core tablet

Mesalamine core tablets were prepared by using wet granulation technique. All the ingredients were weighed separately. Mesalamine USP (API) is passed through #20 sieve, okra gum passed through #40 sieve and mixed thoroughly in rapid mixer granulator and granulated with purified water. The obtained granules were dried in rapid hot air oven until it reaches drying parameters. Dried granules were passed through #20 sieve. These granules were lubricated with flow promoters like magnesium stearate, talc. The flow properties of the granules were determined. The lubricated granules were compressed into tablets using a single punch rotary tablet machine.

S. No	Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
1.	Mesalamine	200	200	200	200	200	200
2.	Xanthan gum	40	60	80	100	120	140
3.	Lactose	146	126	106	86	66	46
4.	Talc	8	8	8	8	8	8
5.	Magnesium stearate	6	6	6	6	6	6
6.	Iso propyl alcohol	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s
7.	Total weight	400	400	400	400	400	400

TABLE 2 : Formulation of Mesalamine Tablets

Evaluation studies

The prepared core and sustained release tablets were evaluated for following parameters like weight variation (Average weight of 20 tablets by electronic weighing balance, Hardness measured by hardness tester, Friability was examined using USP apparatus (Roche friabilator) at 100 revolutions per minute (rpm), and thickness was measured in millimeters (mm) using a Vernier Calliper. Disintegration in 0.1N in HCL and dissolution studies and results were mentioned in table 6 and 9.

Disintegration Test

One tablet was placed in each tube of the basket for tablet disintegration, and the top half of each tube was covered with a disc. To check for coat damage, tablets were initially tested in 0.1N HCl for 2 hours (simulated stomach transit time) at temperature 37°C±0.5°C

Dissolution studies

By carrying out in vitro drug release experiments under circumstances simulating the mouth to colon, it was determined if the tablets of mesalamine had the capacity to remain intact and release the active component in the physiological environment of the stomach, small intestine, and colon. The drug release studies were carried out by using USP

dissolution apparatus type 2 (paddle) at 100 rpm and 37°±0.5°C. Drug release was first examined in 500mL of 0.1N HCl for 2 hours at 100rpm, then 3hours in 900 mL pH 6.0 at 100rpm, 12hours in 900 mL pH 7.2 at 50rpm. Mesalamine analysis was carried out using UV detection at 232 nm in the acid stage and 301 nm in the buffer stage.

Assay

5mL of 0.25N HCl and 50.0g of the mesalamine standard should be added to a 50mL volumetric flask. Mix after dilution to volume and sonicating to dissolve. To create a 160ppm standard solution, pipette 4 mL of this standard stock solution into a 25 mL volumetric flask, dilution to volume, and mixing. Use a 0.45 µm membrane filter to filter. Crush 20 tablets with a weight of about the same to create the sample solution. Fill a 500 mL volumetric flask with precisely weighed powder equal to 800 mg of mesalamine. Add 50 mL of 1N HCl solution, and sonicate for 30 minutes at a temperature below 30 °C while occasionally shaking. Add 300 mL of water, sonicate it for 20 minutes at a temperature below 30 °C while shaking it intermittently, and then dilute it with water to the desired level. Using a 0.45-µm membrane filter, centrifuge a portion of this solution at 3500 rpm for 5 minutes.

Stability studies

The optimized coated formulation was maintained at 40°C with 75% RH , and samples were collected at 0, 10, 20, and 30 days for physical and in-vitro drug release examination.

Results and discussion

Determination of λ max of mesalamine

- The λ max of the mesalamine was found to be 330 nm.

Calibration curve of mesalamine

The absorbance of mesalamine is measured in a UV spectrophotometer at 330nm by using phosphate buffer at pH 6.8 as blank.

- Prepare a stock solution (by dissolving 50 mg

mesalamine in phosphate buffer pH 6.8 and make up to 100 mL (500 μ g/ml). prepare a series of dilutions such as 5, 10, 15, 20, and 25 (μ g/ml) concentrations by using stock sol.

- Measure the absorbance of each dilution at 330nm using UV- Visible spectrophotometer.
- Plot the graph b/w absorbance (y axis) against the concentration (x- axis) using a computer program to perform a linear regression and determine the best – fit line.
- This curve is used to determine the concentration of an unknown sample.

S.No.	Concentration (μ g/ml)	Absorbance
1	0	0
2	5	0.052
3	10	0.104
4	15	0.156
5	20	0.209
6	25	0.261
7	30	0.313

TABLE 3: SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DATA FOR THE ESTIMATION OF MESALAMINE IN PHOSPHATE BUFFER

FIG 1: CALIBRATION CURVE OF MESALAMINE IN PHOSPHATE BUFFER PH6.8.

Compatibility studies using FT- IR

FIG 2: IR SPECTRUM OF PURE DRUG MESALAMINE .

Pre-compression parameter

Formulation number	Bulk density (gm/cc)	Tapped Density (gm/cc)	Carr's index(%)	Hausner's ratio	Angle of repose
F1	0.48±0.01	0.56±0.003	14.28±0.42	1.16±0.006	27.4±0.36
F2	0.49±0.02	0.57±0.002	14.03±0.38	1.16±0.004	26.18±0.41
F3	0.50±0.01	0.58±0.004	13.79±0.55	1.15±0.007	25.36±0.31
F4	0.52±0.02	0.59±0.003	11.86±0.61	1.15±0.005	24.04±0.29
F5	0.53±0.01	0.60±0.002	11.66±0.72	1.13±0.009	23.82±0.34
F6	0.54±0.02	0.61±0.006	11.47±0.84	1.12±0.011	22.15±0.27

TABLE 4: Evaluation parameters of pre – formulation characters of powder blend

All the results of pre compression parameters are found to be within the limits

Physical evaluation of tablets

After compression various quality control tests were carried out , which demonstrated following organoleptic properties viz. colour, odourless and round , flat on both sides.

Organoleptic parameters

Formulation	Colour	Odour	Shape
F1	Off - White colour	Odour less	round ,flat on both sides.
F2	Off - White colour	Odour less	round ,flat on both sides.
F3	Off - White colour	Odour less	round , flat on both sides.
F4	Off - White colour	Odour less	round , flat on both sides.
F5	Off - White colour	Odour less	round , flat on both sides.
F6	Off - White colour	Odour less	round , flat on both sides.

TABLE 5: ORGANOLEPTIC PROPERTIES OF PREPARED TABLETS

POST COMPRESSION PARAMETERS

Formulation	Diameter (mm)	Thickness (mm)	Weight variation (mg)	Hardness (kg/cm ²⁺)	Friability (%)	Drug content (%)
F1	7.82±0.01	4.12±0.03	398±2.4	4.6±0.21	0.62±0.04	98.0±0.72
F2	7.80±0.02	4.15±0.04	401±2.1	5.2±0.18	0.58±0.03	98.5±0.65
F3	7.85±0.07	4.18±0.07	399±1.9	5.8±0.23	0.54±0.05	99.4±0.58
F4	7.84±0.01	4.21±0.04	402±2.3	6.8±0.20	0.49±0.04	99.8±60
F5	7.89±0.01	4.24±0.02	400±2.0	6.9±0.19	0.45±0.03	100.1±0.55
F6	7.94±0.06	4.28±0.03	401±2.2	7.3±0.22	0.41±0.02	100.6±0.48

TABLE 6 : POST-COMPRESSION PARAMETERS

- Thickness of tablet
- Hardness
- Friability
- Weight variation
- Disintegration

In- vitro drug release study

For the determination of the in- vitro drug release of formulation, all the formulated tablets were evaluated for in-vitro dissolution as described in the methodology. The optimized formulation F6 showed the best drug release of 97.6%. In vitro dissolution studies reported the formulation containing okra gum powder demonstrated the best release of the drug at the end of 24 hours.

Cumulative percentage of drug release

Time (hrs.)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
1	20.5±0.9	16.2±0.7	14.2±0.6	11.6±0.5	9.4±0.4	8.2±0.5
2	35.8±1.2	30.4±1.0	26.5±0.9	21.8±0.8	17.3±0.7	14.5±0.7
4	55.6±1.5	48.7±1.3	42.3±1.2	35.6±1.2	28.9±1.0	22.8±0.9
8	83.4±2.0	75.6±1.8	68.4±1.6	60.7±1.4	50.8±1.3	41.6±1.2
12	98.6±2.2	92.4±2.0	86.5±1.6	79.5±1.6	70.4±1.5	63.8±1.3
24	-	97.8±2.1	97.6±2.1	98.5±2.2	96.4±2.0	97.2±1.6

TABLE 7 : IN-VITRO DRUG RELEASE STUDY

- F1 fastest release (completed ~12 hrs)
- F2 ~ 16hrs release
- F3 ~ 20hrs release
- F4&F5 ~control release
- F6 best sustain release upto 24 hrs

Release kinetic studies

Formulation	Zero order (R ²)	First Order (R ²)	Higuchi Plots (R ²)	Korsmeyer Peppas plots (R ²)	n value	Best fit model	Drug release mechanism
F1	0.964	0.93	0.982	0.955	0.51	Higuchi	Diffusion
F2	0.971	0.938	0.987	0.961	0.55	Higuchi	Diffusion
F3	0.975	0.940	0.988	0.970	0.5	Higuchi	Anomalous
F4	0.979	0.946	0.989	0.981	0.62	Higuchi	Anomalous
F5	0.973	0.939	0.986	0.988	0.65	Higuchi	Anomalous
F6	0.978	0.942	0.991	0.991	0.67	Higuchi	Diffusion+ erosion

TABLE 8 : RELEASE KINETIC STUDIES

Time (hr)	Cumulative % Release (Q)	100-Q	Log(100-Q)	Sqrt(Time)	Log(Time)	Log(Q)
1	8.2	91.8	1.962	1	0	0.914
2	14.5	85.5	1.932	1.414	0.301	1.161
4	22.8	77.2	1.888	2	0.602	1.358
8	41.6	58.4	1.766	2.828	0.903	1.619
12	63.8	36.2	1.559	3.464	1.079	1.805
24	97.2	2.8	0.447	4.899	1.38	1.988

Table 9 : Calculation Table
ZERO ORDERFIG 3 : ZERO ORDER KINETICS (FOR F6)
FIRST ORDER

FIG 4 : FIRST ORDER KINETICS (FOR F6)

HIGUCHI PLOT

**FIG 5 : HIGUCHI MODEL (FOR F6)
KORSMEYER- PEPPAS PLOT**

FIG 6 : KORSMEYER-PEPPAS MODEL PLOT (F6)

The plots of cumulative percentage drug release V/s. time, cumulative percent drug retained V/s. root time, log cumulative percent drug retained V/s. time and log cumulative percent drug release V/s. log time were drawn and represented graphically as shown in figure respectively. The slopes and the regression coefficient of determinations (r^2) were listed in table 15. The coefficient of determination indicates that the release data best fitted with zero order kinetics.

Stability studies :

Based on the results of in vitro drug release the best formulation F6 was selected for 1 months

stability studies at the 25°C/60%RH and at the 45°C/75%RH. The stability studies revealed that there was no any significant degradation of the drug.

Stability studies were carried out for the optimized formulation (F6) of mesalamine sustained release tablets prepared using a natural polymer.

Based on in-vitro drug release results, the best formulation was subjected to stability testing for 1 months under the following conditions as per ICH guidelines:

25°C ± 2°C / 60% ± 5% RH

40°C ± 2°C / 75% ± 5% RH

Storage period	Stored at 25°C/60% RH				Stored at 40°C/75% RH			
	Formulation F6				Formulation F6			
	Hardness (Kg/cm ²)	% Friability	% Drug Content	% CDR	Hardness (Kg/cm ²)	% Friability	% Drug Content	% CDR
Initial	7.3±0.22	0.41±0.04	100.6±0.51	97.2±1.6	7.3±0.22	0.41±0.04	100.6±0.51	97.2±1.6
After 10 days	7.0±0.1	0.40±0.2	100.1±0.6	96.5±0.3	5.9±0.14	0.38±0.1	99.4±0.7	96.0±0.3
After 20 days	6.8±0.15	0.39±0.1	99.6±0.4	95.9±0.5	5.5±0.18	0.35±0.2	97.8±0.5	95.1±0.4
After 30 days	6.4±0.10	0.34±0.1	98.8±0.5	94.3±0.4	5.3±0.20	0.34±0.1	96.9±0.6	94.5±0.5

TABLE - 10: STABILITY STUDIE

The tablets were evaluated at 0, 10, 20, 30 days. The results indicated that there were no significant changes in physical characteristics, drug content, and drug release profile during the study period. Hence, the formulation was found to be physically and chemically stable.

REFERENCES:

- Ungaro R, Mehandru S, Allen PB, et al. Ulcerative colitis. 2017;389(10080):1756-70. *Lancet*.
- Danese S, Fiocchi C. Ulcerative colitis. *N Engl J Med*. 2011;365(18):1713-25.
- Ordás I, Eckmann L, Talamini M, et al. Ulcerative colitis. 2012;380(9853):1606-19. *Lancet*.
- Ananthakrishnan AN. Epidemiology and risk factors for IBD. *Nat Rev Gastroenterol Hepatol*. 2015;12(4):205-17.
- Xavier RJ, Podolsky DK. Unravelling the pathogenesis of inflammatory bowel disease. *Nature*. 2007;448(7152):427-34.
- Khor B, Gardet A, Xavier RJ. Genetics and pathogenesis of IBD. 2011;474(7351):307-17. [6] *Nature*.
- Neurath MF. Cytokines in inflammatory bowel disease. *Nat Rev Immunol*. 2014;14(5):329-42. [7]
- Ko JK, Auyeung KK. Inflammatory bowel disease: etiology, pathogenesis, and current therapy. *Curr Pharm Des*. 2014;20(7):1082-96.
- Harbord M, Eliakim R, Bettenworth D, et al. European consensus on diagnosis and management of ulcerative colitis. *J Crohns Colitis*. 2017;11(6):649-70.
- Dignass A, Lindsay JO, Sturm A, et al. Second European evidence-based consensus on the diagnosis and management of UC. *J Crohns Colitis*. 2012;6(10):991-1030.
- Lachman L, Lieberman HA, Kanig JL. The Theory and Practice of Industrial Pharmacy. 3rd ed. Philadelphia: Lea & Febiger; 1986. p. 293-345.
- Aulton ME, Taylor KMG. Aulton's Pharmaceutics: The Design and Manufacture of Medicines. 5th ed. London: Elsevier; 2018. p. 457-482.
- Banker GS, Anderson NR. Tablets. In: Lachman L, Lieberman HA, Kanig JL, editors. The Theory and Practice of Industrial Pharmacy. 3rd ed. Philadelphia: Lea & Febiger; 1986. p. 293-345.
- Ansel HC, Allen LV Jr, Popovich NG. Pharmaceutical Calculations. 15th ed. Philadelphia: Wolters Kluwer; 2021. p. 401-410.
- Aulton ME, Taylor KMG. Aulton's Pharmaceutics: The Design and Manufacture of Medicines. 5th ed. London: Elsevier; 2018. p. 101-110, 365-380.
- Aulton ME, Taylor KMG. Aulton's Pharmaceutics: The Design and Manufacture of Medicines. 5th ed. London: Elsevier; 2018. p. 101-110, 365-380.
- Rowe RC, Sheskey PJ, Quinn ME. Handbook of Pharmaceutical Excipients. 7th ed. London: Pharmaceutical Press; 2012.
- Martin A, Bustamante P, Chun AHC. Physical Pharmacy: Physical Chemical Principles in the Pharmaceutical Sciences. 5th ed. Philadelphia: Lippincott Williams & Wilkins; 2011.
- Lachman L, Lieberman HA, Kanig JL. The Theory and Practice of Industrial Pharmacy. 3rd ed. Bombay: Varghese Publishing House; 1987. p. 128-185.
- Allen LV Jr, Popovich NG, Ansel HC. Ansel's Pharmaceutical Dosage Forms and Drug Delivery Systems. 10th ed. Philadelphia: Wolters Kluwer; 2018.
- Jain NK. Advances in Controlled and Novel Drug Delivery. New Delhi: CBS Publishers;

- 2001.p. 173–205.
22. Remington JP. Remington: The Science and Practice of Pharmacy. 24th ed. Philadelphia: Lippincott Williams & Wilkins; 2011.
 23. Raghavan S, Hodge H. Xanthan gum. In: Rowe RC, Sheskey PJ, Quinn ME, editors. Handbook of Pharmaceutical Excipients. 7th ed. London: Pharmaceutical Press; 2012. p. 788–792.
 24. PVP (Polyvinylpyrrolidone) monograph. In: Rowe RC, Sheskey PJ, Quinn ME, editors. Handbook of Pharmaceutical Excipients. 7th ed. London: Pharmaceutical Press; 2012. p. 610–612.
 25. MCC (Microcrystalline Cellulose) monograph. In: Rowe RC, Sheskey PJ, Quinn ME, editors. Handbook of Pharmaceutical Excipients. London: Pharmaceutical Press; 2012. p. 424–426.
 26. Talc monograph. In: Rowe RC, Sheskey PJ, Quinn ME, editors. Handbook of Pharmaceutical Excipients. London: Pharmaceutical Press; 2012. p. 682–684.
 27. Magnesium stearate monograph. In: Rowe RC, Sheskey PJ, Quinn ME, editors. Handbook of Pharmaceutical Excipients. London: Pharmaceutical Press; 2012. p. 447–449.